

MATERIAL BEHAVIOR OF PREPREGS IN AUTOMATED ROBOTIC SHEET-LAYUP: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

A novel approach to the automated production of complex fiber-reinforced components, while retaining process flexibility, is robotic layup of prepreg sheets. By optimizing path planning for robot trajectory generation and employing specially developed end-effectors, the goal is to achieve error-free placement and forming of the prepreg sheets.

Research to date has focused primarily on the development of a suitable overall system consisting of one or more robots with effector tools. Initial proof-of-concept studies have already been carried out with this overall system. Nevertheless, material behavior and its interaction with the robot-based draping process and the mold geometry were often neglected. However, especially with complex, multi-curved molds, different material properties in combination with different process parameters, such as the layup sequence, lead to a very different end quality. These interactions between material, process and mold geometry must be taken into account when developing suitable robot operations.

This paper, therefore, presents a comprehensive analysis of the behavior of various prepreg materials during robotic sheet layup. The study investigates how different material properties of prepregs influence draping quality by applying different draping strategies to various complex molds. This research is the first to demonstrate the impact of material and process parameters on the fully automated, robotic layup of prepreg sheets.

The results show that various material parameters influence the quality of robot-assisted draping. However, the choice of a layup strategy for the prepreg sheets is more decisive for a good quality. An optimized draping strategy with suitable end effectors can ensure error-free forming of the prepreg sheets with almost all common prepreg materials, even on more complex molds.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have undergone remarkable development in recent years and have established themselves as key materials in many industries. Their versatility, combined with increasing demands for efficiency, sustainability, and performance, has significantly enhanced their relevance. While composite parts have traditionally been used primarily in aerospace and high-performance motorsports, advancements in manufacturing technology, falling raw material prices, and improved availability have extended their application into the automotive industry, construction, and the energy sector. [1 – 3]

The excellent mechanical properties of FRPs largely depend on the fibre materials used and their precise alignment within the component (direction-dependent behavior, known as anisotropy). However, this increases manufacturing complexity, as FRPs must be built up layer by layer. The current state-of-the-art for high performance application is the prepreg process, in which a pre-impregnated textile semi-finished product is manually formed into a near-net-shape geometry and then cured into a finished component in an autoclave process. [4,5]

Forming the flexible, sticky textile layers into the desired three-dimensional shape is time-consuming, error-prone, and—due to the material's specific properties—currently only very limitedly automatable. This forming process (known as draping) requires a sensitive understanding of the material and considerable experience to avoid defects such as wrinkles and voids. Despite this, 30% of continuous

fibre-reinforced components in aerospace are manufactured through draping, with automation implemented in only 5% of those cases. [6]

Experienced and well-trained specialists can process up to 1.15 kg of material per hour. Their sensorimotor skills, cognitive flexibility, and low machine and tooling costs also enable rapid product changeovers. [7] At the same time, manual production leads to high material waste, end-product defects, and - especially in Western countries - high labor costs, making the process uneconomical. Furthermore, unattractive working conditions, which often cause health issues such as wrist or back pain and allergies, are contributing to an increasing shortage of skilled workers. [8]

A promising strategy to reduce manual processes and improve reproducibility is the automation of production. This can save up to 90% of the working time per component and increase material efficiency from around 40% to as much as 95% compared to manual production. Large companies in the aerospace and automotive industries are already using fully automated processes for manufacturing FRP components. [8, 9]

Current automation in the form of Automated Fiber Placement or Automated Tape Laying requires very high investment costs and is also limited to simple component shapes, such as shell geometries. The process also requires long set-up times, which further limits flexibility. For this reason, research has been conducted for some time into a robot-based lay-up process that takes the manual prepreg lay-up process as a model and enables prepreg lay-up and with specialized end effectors and defined trajectories. So far, the focus has been on the development of suitable hardware for draping and holding the prepreg as well as the implementation for individual component shapes. However, for an error-free robot-based prepreg layup, the material properties and different layup strategies must also be taken into account, as these have a significant influence on the layup process. [10 – 12]

For this reason, a material study is presented in which a total of four different materials were tested on four different molds. The focus of the study was to investigate the extent to which individual material properties and different draping strategies influence the quality of the final result.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Robot based prepreg layup

The prepreg layup is defined according to [13] as the spherical forming of planar reinforcement textiles into near-net-shape component geometries. The transformation of the textiles takes place under the influence of external forces. This forming process has a significant impact on the mechanical and optical properties of the final component. The draping result is determined by the process, the material, and the component geometry [14,15]. Various draping strategies are used to drape the textiles.

Robot-assisted draping is a promising approach for automating the prepreg layup process in the production of fiber-reinforced components. To achieve the goal of near-complete automation, an intelligent robot-assisted manufacturing system is employed, which automates the draping process, thereby ensuring consistent quality, increased productivity, and reduced labor costs. [11,12,16]

Such a system typically consists of a hybrid robot cell with multiple robot arms or a single robot arm in combination with a holding fixture. These components work closely together to grasp, position, and apply the material to a mold. Specialized end effectors are used, which form the prepreg onto the mold contour with appropriate force and precision using rollers. To avoid defects such as wrinkles or air inclusions, controlled tension during draping is required. This is achieved through the use of robots with integrated force control or a dedicated holding fixture. [11,12,16]

2.2 Draping Defects and Their Influencing Parameters

Regardless of whether a manual or robot-based draping process is used, draping effects occur during the forming of reinforcement textiles. These effects alter the fiber orientation compared to the target position and should therefore be minimized, as they—like previously mentioned—negatively impact the optical and mechanical properties of the final component [17]. A variety of draping defects are distinguished, typically classified into two-dimensional and three-dimensional defects. Two-dimensional defects include fiber undulations and gaps, while three-dimensional defects comprise wrinkles and loops. In general, the frequency and severity of draping effects correlate with the geometric

complexity of the component in automated forming processes [17,18]

The occurrence of draping defects is primarily influenced by the component geometry, the type of process, and the textile properties. Such defects are more likely to occur on component geometries featuring high aspect ratios, small radii, sharp angles, and strong curvatures. From a process perspective, draping defects are mainly promoted by relative movements between the tool and the textile, foreign particles, or excessive applied forces. However, the textile used has the most significant influence on the occurrence or prevention of draping defects. Key textile parameters include the type of textile, weave pattern, areal weight, roving material, and laminate structure. [18]

The emergence of draping defects is linked to various physical effects, with the so-called Trellis effect being predominant. The Trellis effect describes the shearing of a woven fabric. Shearing occurs when external tensile forces act on the rovings in directions other than the principal fiber orientation. As the degree of shear increases, friction between the intersecting rovings rises, requiring greater force to continue shearing. The shear force can increase until a material-specific critical shear angle is reached. Beyond this angle, the shear can no longer be accommodated within the plane of the fabric. Shearing beyond the critical angle inevitably leads to draping defects, which must be avoided. The extent of draping effects is highly dependent on the choice of textile semi-finished product and its drapability. Textiles that allow higher shear with lower shear resistance generally enable better forming quality. [18]

3 METHOD AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of different prepreg materials and different layup strategies on the draping quality in a robot-based sheet layup process. However, the study does not solely focus on the drapability of various materials or layup strategies; rather, it places particular emphasis on analyzing the interdependencies between process parameter, layup strategy, the geometry of the mold, and the type of textile reinforcement. Accordingly, the material study is structured using a two-stage approach.

3.1 Examination of drapability with regard to the material parameters

Initially, four materials were examined on two different mold geometries. To do this, a preliminary selection of ten commonly available prepreg materials from the market was made. From these ten materials, four were selected for testing. The selection focused on the main influencing factors, namely the type of weave, fabric weight, and weave pattern. Additionally, the materials were chosen in such a way that non-investigated factors—such as the matrix type—remained consistent across all selected materials. Table 1 presents the tested materials along with their respective parameters.

Material	Prepreg variant	Type of binding	Grammage
Nr 1	Roving	Plain weave	200 gsm
Nr. 2	Roving	Twill weave	200 gsm
Nr. 3	Roving	Twill weave	410 gsm
Nr. 4	Towpreg	Plain weave	76 gsm

Table 1: Tested Materials

The focus of this experiment was to investigate the drapability of the materials with respect to their inherent properties, without a detailed analysis of the influences from the robot's draping strategy or the mold geometry. For this reason, an ideal strategy for the robot-based draping was defined by an expert. The selected molds feature relatively simple geometries to ensure that process- and geometry-related parameters do not overshadow the textile properties. The following figure shows the two molds along with the draping strategy applied by the robot.

Figure 1: Used molds and corresponding trajectories

For the implementation of the draping strategies, a Universal Robot UR5e was used, featuring a payload capacity of 5 kg and a reach of 850 mm. In addition, custom-developed end effectors were employed—some designed for universal use across a wide range of geometric features, and others specifically engineered for one of the component geometries presented in this study. An integrated impedance controller was used to enable simultaneous position and force control. The initial positioning on a specific geometry element of the corresponding mold was carried out manually to ensure precise alignment. To allow for fully automated draping, an automatic tool changer was also utilized. Figure 2 shows the end effectors used as well as the complete robotic cell employed for the tests.

The evaluation of the layup quality was carried out using the method developed by Schöfer [15]. This assessment methodology enables a quantitative evaluation of quality by relating the severity of defects (G_i), the frequency and size of defects (A_i), and the distance of each defect from the component's symmetry axis (a_i) to the total component area (A_{ges}) and the maximum possible distance from the symmetry axis (a_{max}). Based on these parameters a defect index (FI) can be calculated using the following formula, where a defect index of 0 represents perfect quality:

$$FI = 100 * \sum_i^k G_i * \left(\frac{A_i}{A_{ges}} * \left(1 - \frac{a_i}{a_{max}} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

This method allows for a direct comparison between the individual materials. To eliminate process-related uncertainties, each trial was performed five times. In addition to the qualitative evaluation of the layup, process efficiency was also examined by measuring the cycle time.

Figure 2: robot tools and used setup for the study

3.2 Investigation of drapability with respect to draping strategy and form complexity

Based on the results from the first part of the material study, the best-performing material was selected for the second part of the investigation. This material was then subjected to further testing with varying process parameters by applying different layup strategies on significantly more complex mold geometries. The two molds from the first part of the study were reused, along with two additional molds featuring considerably higher geometric complexity. The two new geometries are characterized by inward-facing corners that require very high textile shear in order to achieve a defect-free layup. However, the level of shear remains below the critical shear angle, meaning both geometries are still suitable for flawless draping.

The focus of this part of the study was to examine the extent to which different robot layup strategies and the complexity of the mold geometry influence the final layup quality. For each of the four tested geometries, three distinct layup strategies were developed by an expert and implemented by the robot in the same manner as in the first part of the study. The evaluation of quality was again performed using the Schöfer method [15]. The following Figure 3 illustrates the draping strategies applied to the four component geometries.

Figure 3: Layup strategies

The aim of this part of the study was to investigate the interaction between the material and various draping strategies. For this section, three identical trials were carried out for each case to eliminate process-related uncertainties.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results of the study are presented below. The results are divided into several parts. Firstly, the results of the first part of the study are presented. In particular, the individual material parameters and their effects are discussed. The second part of the evaluation then examines the interactions between the material and various draping strategies.

4.1 Results of the material influence parameters on the quality of the robot-based prepreg layup

To determine the influence of material parameters, a fractional factorial experimental design was chosen, as shown in the following table. In the first test series, a roving prepreg was compared with a towpreg. Both materials feature a plain weave and have an areal weight of 200 gsm and 76 gsm, respectively. The second test series examines the influence of the weave type by comparing two roving prepregs, each with an areal weight of 200 gsm—one with a plain weave and the other with a twill weave. The third key influence parameter, the material weight, was investigated using two prepregs with a twill weave and areal weights of 200 gsm and 410 gsm.

Test series	Prepreg variant	Type of binding	Grammage
Nr 1	Roving	Plain weave	200 gsm
	Towpreg	Plain weave	76 gsm
Nr. 2	Roving	Twill weave	200 gsm
	Roving	Plain weave	200 gsm
Nr. 3	Roving	Twill weave	200 gsm
	Roving	Twill weave	410 gsm

Table 2: Material parameters tested in the first part of the study

First, the T-profile was draped and evaluated according to the experimental plan shown in table 2. Table 3 presents the average defect indices from all five trials. In terms of defect types, almost exclusively wrinkles occurred during the draping. No gaps or loops were observed, and fiber undulations were rare to non-existent. The table shows that neither the weave type nor the areal weight leads to a significant difference in the draping quality. Only the towpreg exhibited noticeably poorer quality.

This indicates that, for simple geometries that do not require textile shearing, the robot is able to handle and process both plain and twill weave fabrics equally well. The prepreg weight also plays a minor role in the robotic process. The end-effectors are capable of manipulating both lightweight and heavyweight prepregs. However, the towpreg cannot be processed satisfactorily by the robot. The towpreg used in this study is very tightly woven and thus extremely resistant to deformation. In addition, it allows almost no air permeability between the crossover points, of which there are very few due to the inherent characteristics of towpreg. As a result of the high inter-fiber friction and lack of permeability, the robot's end-effectors are unable to adequately conform the prepreg even to simple geometries.

According to the experimental plan from Table 2, the same tests were also carried out on the drone propeller blade shown in Figure 1. Here, similar results in draping quality were observed as with the T-profile. Wrinkles again appeared most frequently, while no gaps or loops and only minimal fiber undulations were present. The average defect index increased significantly for all four materials compared to the T-profile (see Table 2). This is due to the considerably more complex geometry. In particular, the root area of the propeller blade with its very tight radius, requires textile shearing, which the robot's end-effectors can only apply to a limited extent.

Nevertheless, even for this mold, the influence of weight and weave type on the robot-based prepreg layup remains minor. In contrast, draping using a towpreg is significantly worse than with a roving prepreg. As previously explained, this is primarily due to the weave structure and high inter-fiber friction of the towpreg material.

Material	Mean error index T-profil	Mean error index P-profil
Nr 1	0,64	4,19
Nr. 2	0,65	4,83
Nr. 3	0,0	4,28
Nr. 4	3,11	18,74

Table 3: Mean error index of the tested materials

In addition to evaluating draping quality using the Schöfer method [15], the study also analyzed where most defects occurred within the component geometries. For the T-profile, only a few defects were observed, and these could not be assigned to any specific region. Except for the towpreg, the observed defects were primarily due to process uncertainties in the robotic draping process, which could likely be eliminated through iterative process refinement.

For the propeller shape, defects—consistent with previous observations—were concentrated mainly in the root area of the blade. This is primarily due to insufficient textile shearing, which is required to conform the material to the tight radii in that region.

In summary, different material parameters have only a limited influence on the draping quality in robot-based prepreg layup when applied to simple geometries. Only the towpreg proved unsuitable for robotic draping due to its structural characteristics. However, the experiments also clearly showed that the most critical factors influencing the final draping quality are the complexity of the mold geometry and the robotic draping process itself. For this reason, the second part of the study focuses on investigating the interaction between form geometry, robotic strategy, and material behavior.

4.2 Influence of draping strategy and form complexity on robot-based prepreg layup

To investigate the interaction between the material, the robot process, and the form geometry, the molds and robot strategies described in Chapter 3.2 were used. Since the total test space with four molds, three robot strategies, and four materials would have resulted in 48 combinations that each needed to be tested at least three times, we decided to test only one material. This decision was based on previous results, which showed that material parameters have a less decisive impact on achieving good quality in robot-based draping. The chosen material was a twill weave with a weight of 200 gsm, as it is the most common material on the market and can be used in nearly all applications.

Initially, the T-profile and the propeller profile were draped again by the robot using the respective end effectors. Table 4 shows the average error index of the three identical trials for each case along with the standard deviation. Analysis of the results shows that the draping strategy has a significant influence on the final quality. Using strategies similar to those from the first part of the study (see Chapter 4.1), very good results with error indices of 0.308 and 2.584 were achieved. The two other strategies for the T-profile and the P-profile resulted in higher but still acceptable error indices. These results demonstrate that the choice of draping strategy also has a decisive impact on draping quality, even for simple form geometries. In particular, the choice of the starting point is crucial. If it is not optimally selected, there is a risk during robot-based draping that the textile can no longer adapt to the form because it is already fixed at too many points, which prevents any movement.

However, not only the choice of a suitable draping strategy is important for good draping quality. For all three strategies and both components, errors appear consistently in specific regions. As already observed in the first part of the study, errors on the propeller profile mainly occur in the complex root area (see Figure 4). For the T-profile, errors are also visible in more complex regions such as vertical surfaces and inner radii

Figure 4: Regions, where errors occurred during the layup process

These two experiments have shown that, with the current draping process, less complex mold geometries can be draped with a very good result, when using an appropriate draping strategy. To analyze the interaction between draping strategy, material, and complex form geometries in more detail, the two additional shapes (see Chapter 3.2) were draped and analyzed in a subsequent step using three different strategies and one material (twill weave, 200 gsm).

With an error index ranging from 1.07 to 19.43 for the K-profile and from 7.71 to 51.154 (see Table 4), the quality for both molds is significantly lower due to the high form complexity. Furthermore, the quality, expressed by the error index, varies much more between the individual strategies for these two components than for the previously tested parts. This indicates a strong interaction between the chosen draping strategy and the form complexity. Critical influences on quality include the selection of the starting point and the sequence of the individual draping paths. It is crucial that the textile can be sheared by the end effectors for as long as possible. Additionally, strategies in which the draping movements proceed toward the outer edges of the part lead to better results than those where the movements go toward the center of the component. In the following figure the results of the three draping strategies for the k-profile are shown.

Figure 5: Draping results for the k-profile

Figure 6 assigns the errors to specific regions of the components. It is evident that the errors primarily occur where high textile shear takes place. For the K-profile, this is especially the case at the ramps, where the folds arise due to the strong shear required at the inner edge. For the G-profile, the errors are

distributed across the entire mold, but here too, it can be seen that the errors mainly occur in areas where significant textile shear occurs.

Figure 5: Regions, where errors occurred during the layup process

The experiments on the K-profile and G-profile have shown that there is a very strong interaction between the draping strategy and the form complexity. It is even more important than with simple geometries to choose the appropriate draping strategy. In particular, selecting the correct starting point, determining the proper sequence of individual draping movements, and defining the direction of these movements are crucial for achieving good results.

Test series	Mean error index	Standard deviation
T-Profil 1	1,794	1,559
T-Profil 2	4,775	0,279
T-Profil 3	0,308	0,154
P-Profil 1	7,606	8,809
P-Profil 2	5,183	1,202
P-Profil 3	2,584	0,705
G-Profil 1	51,154	1
G-Profil 2	16,066	3,729
G-Profil 3	7,707	3
K-Profil 1	12,460	11,878
K-Profil 2	4,269	2,895
K-Profil 3	19,426	5,166

Table 4: Material parameters tested in the first part of the study

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, the robot-assisted layup process of prepregs was analyzed with regard to the influence of different material parameters, the selected draping strategy, and the complexity of the part geometry. In the first part of the study, various material parameters and their impact on layup quality were evaluated. The second part focused specifically on investigating the extent to which the choice of draping strategy and the complexity of the part affect the final layup quality. A total of 40 trials were conducted

to test three material parameters on two shapes, and 36 trials were performed to evaluate three draping strategies on four different geometries.

It was found that material parameters such as weave type and areal weight have no significant impact on the quality of the final product. This indicates that all common prepreg materials can be used in a robot-based layup process.

The trials involving different draping strategies on geometries of varying complexity showed that selecting a well-suited draping strategy is crucial. In particular, the starting point and the sequence of individual draping steps must be defined with care. Furthermore, it is not only necessary for the end effectors to enable the forming of the textile, but also to actively induce textile shearing during the process so that even complex part geometries can be draped without defects.

Future research should therefore focus on the development of suitable draping strategies that can be applied to a wide range of part geometries. In this context, the analysis of manual draping motions and their abstraction and transfer to robotic processes can be especially helpful. In addition, a holding mechanism should be developed that enables targeted shearing of the prepreg during the process, thus improving the ability to prevent wrinkle formation in robotic layups.

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